

[Elly Kleinman Americare](#) offers the superior qualifications of each member of working staff. People working at Elly Kleinman Americare are very aware of the emotional, physical, and financial stress that is associated with caring for a loved one at home.

A quick placement of care is a must at Americare as the professional staff works hard to provide its patients with the answers and services that fit their needs.

Taking care of patient's medical needs and finding the right services can be a very daunting and complicated task. Social workers at Elly Kleinman Americare work with each patient over every step of the way to help them navigate through and identify the services that will meet their individual needs.

Elly Kleinman Americare stands behind company's commitment of availability. In most cases, the large staff allows the management to provide immediate services and replacements if necessary at a moments notice. Whether it's a holiday or a weekend or just an average weekday Americare is right where patients need them the most - at their home. Currently, Elly Kleinman Americare headquarters are in Brooklyn, from where the company provides its services over five boroughs of New York.

Working closely with hospitals and doctors for Elly Kleinman Americare is a vital step towards patient's recovery. When requested, a registered nurse can come to the hospital to do a preliminary assessment of patient's needs. The company works closely with the patient's doctor, medical professional and social worker to find the best program of care that will ensure the patient's transition back to its home go as smoothly as possible.

As the CEO of Americare, [Elly Kleinman](#) has a deep commitment to patient satisfaction, which has been proven many times over the past 30 years. Their Patient Relations Department is there to give patients a direct line of contact.